

IMPROVING LEARNERS PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE USE OF PROCESS ORIENTED GUIDED INQUIRY LEARNING (POGIL) ACTIVITY SHEET: A GAS LAWS EXAMPLE

Iohannes Paoli B. Baldomar, LPT, PhD

Science Department, Taft National High School, Taft, Eastern Samar, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13636262>

ABSTRACT

The academic performance of Filipino learners in science has been a concern due to consistently low ratings in various assessments. This study investigates the effectiveness of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets in teaching gas laws to grade 10 learners. The research design includes a quasi-experimental approach with matched subjects and a Solomon Four-Group Design. The participants consist of 40 struggling learners, divided into two control and two experimental groups. Pretest results reveal no significant difference between control and experimental groups. However, posttest results show significantly higher scores in experimental groups, indicating the positive impact of POGIL activity sheets. Statistical analysis confirms the effectiveness of POGIL-based teaching approach in enhancing learners' performance. Additionally, learners' feedback indicates that POGIL activity sheets are effective in helping them understand Gas Laws, aligning with the constructivist theory of learning. In conclusion, POGIL activity sheets are an effective instructional strategy for improving the academic performance of Filipino learners in science, particularly in challenging topics like gas laws, offering a student-centered, inquiry-based approach to learning.

Keywords: *Science Learners, Academic Performance, Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL), Gas laws.*

INTRODUCTION

The academic performance of Filipino learners in science has been inadequate. This is evidenced by various assessments conducted both locally and internationally. For example, the National Achievement Test (NAT) for the school year 2017-2018 showed that Grade 10 learners had low ratings in core learning areas, particularly in problem solving, information literacy, and critical thinking skills. Science had the lowest performance, with a mean percentage score of 44.59, which indicates a "low mastery" level of performance (Albano, 2019). Similarly, the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) showed that Philippine learners' achievement in science and mathematics remains below the international average (Masigan, 2021). This suggests that there is a need for educational interventions to improve students' performance in these subjects. The TIMSS 2019 results showed that Filipino learners struggle to apply their knowledge to real-world contexts. This reflects a gap in their conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills (OECD, 2019). The PISA framework, which evaluates students' proficiency in scientific literacy, highlights the importance of inquiry-based learning methods that engage students actively in the learning process (OECD, 2019). These findings underscore the importance of adopting effective instructional strategies to address identified challenges and promote learners' conceptual understanding.

One potential instructional method that holds promise for improving learners' performance is Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL). Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) is an active learning strategy that promotes collaborative and inquiry-based learning experiences, where students work in small groups to solve problems, analyze data, and construct knowledge. (Rodriguez, Lazenby, et al., 2020; Wijaya & Handayani, 2021) The POGIL model represents a student-centered approach to learning, emphasizing active participation and group cooperation within the classroom setting to foster a deeper understanding of concepts. (Fitriani, Irwandi, & Murniati, 2017) This method emphasizes the importance of allowing students ample opportunities to analyze questions, draw conclusions, develop concepts, solve open-ended problems, and evaluate and reflect on their discoveries. By implementing the POGIL learning approach, students are empowered to take charge of their own learning within the group setting. (Saputro, Rohaeti, & Prodjosantoso, 2018) The choice to focus on gas laws is motivated by the complexity and abstract nature of this topic, which often poses difficulties for learners. The traditional lecture-based approach in often leads to passive learning and limited comprehension, resulting in poor academic performance (Villagonzalo, 2014). By adopting POGIL activity sheets in teaching gas laws, students are actively involved in the learning process, allowing them to explore the fundamental principles, relationships, and applications of gas laws through hands-on activities.

POGIL activity sheets are a structured framework for collaborative learning that encourages students to work in small groups to solve guided inquiry questions. (Spencer & Silverman, 2001; Uche & Eze, 2018) By engaging in the inquiry process, students actively construct their knowledge, make connections, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The collaborative nature of POGIL fosters

communication and teamwork, allowing students to learn from each other's perspectives and build their problem-solving skills. POGIL activity sheets are designed to promote critical thinking and higher-order cognitive skills. These activities present students with authentic, real-life scenarios and open-ended questions that require analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. By challenging students to think critically, the POGIL activity sheets help them develop a deeper understanding of the underlying principles of gas laws and enhance their ability to apply these concepts in different contexts. The use of POGIL activity sheets in teaching gas laws aligns with current educational trends that emphasize student-centered, active learning approaches. It addresses the need for instructional strategies that promote conceptual understanding, scientific inquiry, and the development of 21st-century skills. By incorporating POGIL activity sheets into the gas laws curriculum, educators can create an engaging learning environment that supports student learning and facilitates the development of key competencies.

Although many studies have investigated the relationship between POGIL and academic performance, the findings have been inconsistent. For example, Walker et al. (2017) found that POGIL had a small effect on student achievement in college chemistry, but this effect was not considered educationally meaningful. This inconsistency highlights the need for further research to better understand the true effects of POGIL on academic performance.

The intervention implemented in this study centers on the development and utilization of a POGIL activity sheet specifically designed for gas laws. The activity sheet acts as a roadmap, guiding students through a structured process of inquiry and discovery. It prompts learners to think critically, analyze data, draw connections, and construct their own knowledge. Through this intervention, students are empowered to take ownership of their learning journey, fostering a sense of autonomy and self-directedness.

The findings of this study will contribute to the existing body of research on instructional strategies in science education, particularly in the context of teaching gas laws. By investigating the effectiveness of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets, this study aims to provide insights into the potential benefits of this approach in improving learners' performance and understanding of complex scientific concepts. The results may inform educators and curriculum developers in designing instructional materials and strategies that promote active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of using Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets on learners' performance, specifically in the context of understanding gas laws.

Research Questions

This study investigated the effectiveness of POGIL-AS in teaching gas laws to grade 10 learners. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the pre-test percentage scores of the control and experimental groups?

2. Is there a significant difference between the pretest percentage scores of the two groups?
3. What is the post-test percentage scores of the four groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test percentage scores of the control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference among the post-test percentage scores of the four groups?
6. What is the perceptions of respondents towards the use of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) Activity Sheets in teaching gas laws?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a quasi-experimental approach with matched subjects to select 40 grade 10 learners as participants. Fraenkel and Wallen (2000) describe this type of design as one in which individuals are paired on the basis of specific variables to establish group equivalence and mitigate any potential impact on the study. Random assignment was not possible in this study because the subject groups were intact. Educational authorities typically prohibit the disbandment and reconstitution of classes solely for research purposes, making the chosen research method the only viable option. To address the research questions, the study used a Solomon Four-Group Design (Campbell & Stanley, 1966). This study involved four groups: two experimental groups and two control groups. One control group had a pretest, while the other control group did not. In the Experimental Groups, one experimental group had a pretest, and the other experimental group did not receive a pretest. After the pretest, all four groups received instruction, with the experimental groups using POGIL activity sheets, and the control groups using conventional instructional methods. Finally, a posttest was administered to all groups to assess their learning outcomes. In addition, a survey questionnaire was used to gather the learners' views about using Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) Activity Sheets in teaching gas laws.

Research Participants

The research participants included a total of 40 Grade 10 participants from Taft National High School for the school year 2022-2023. The participants were divided into four groups for the study. The first group, referred to as CG1, consisted of the Amethyst section learners and served as the control group with a pretest. The second group, CG2, comprised learners from the Pearl section and also served as a control group, but without a pretest. The third group, EG1, consisted of learners from the Jade section and was assigned as the experimental group with a pretest. Finally, the fourth group, EG2, comprised learners from the Diamond section and served as the experimental group without a pretest. The participants in this study were identified as struggling learners, indicating that they faced difficulties in their academic performance. Each group consisted of 10 participants, resulting in a total of 40 learners participating in the research. By

including learners from different sections and assigning them to specific groups, this study aimed to assess the impact of the Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheet on learners' performance in the context of gas laws.

Before being included in the study, parental consent was required from all participants. All forms of participation occurred within the context of in-person classes.

Research Instrument

A. Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning Activity Sheet

The researcher developed Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL)-Activity Sheets (AS) to teach gas laws in Science 10. The researcher believed that POGIL-AS would help students with their difficulty in solving science problems and address the lack of instructional materials. The POGIL-AS was a teacher-made instructional material designed to help learners master a competency-based skill that they were not able to develop in the self-learning modules. The POGIL-AS was designed to meet the learning needs of the learners. Five Science Master Teachers validated the POGIL-AS based on five indicators: objectives, content, format and language, presentation, and usefulness.

B. Teacher Made-Test

The researcher constructed a pretest and posttest consisting of 20 multiple-choice items with four options each, covering competencies in Gas Laws. To ensure the content validity of the test, a table of specifications was created. The test was first submitted to science teachers that were experts in the field for their feedback. Their suggestions for improving the test were noted.

The first draft of the assessment test was administered to 10 students per strata or group based on their academic performance. The students' responses were scored as "0" for every incorrect answer and "1" for every correct answer for each test item. The internal consistency method was used to determine the reliability of the final draft of the assessment questionnaire. This method was considered the most appropriate since the test consisted of two distinct results—the examinee either passed or failed in an item. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was computed to determine if the instrument had the right internal consistency or if the instrument was acceptable (George & Mallery, 2003). This meant that if the correlations were lower than 0.3, an item might have been problematic and had to be removed to make the questionnaire reliable.

C. Respondents' Feedback on the use of POGIL in the Teaching Gas Laws Survey

The researcher developed a survey questionnaire to assess students' perceptions of POGIL. The survey included questions about students' understanding of gas laws, their satisfaction with the POGIL activities, and their perceived effectiveness of POGIL in

helping them learn gas laws. The survey questionnaire was validated by master teachers in the science department and one English master teacher.

RESULTS

Table 1. The percentage scores in the pretest of the control and experimental Groups

Groups	PS	TG	Description
Control Group 1 (CG1)	17.5%	64%	Did Not Meet Expectations
Experimental Group (EG1)	16.5%	64%	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 2. Difference between the percentage scores of the two groups in the pretest

t critical value	t computed value	Level of Significance	df	Decision on H_{01}	Interpretation
2.101	1.2231	0.05	18	Fail to reject the null hypothesis	Not significant

Table 3. The percentage scores in the posttest of the four groups

Groups	PS	TG	Description
Control Group 1 (CG1)	61	76	Fairly Satisfactory
Control Group 2 (CG2)	55	73	Did Not Meet Expectations
Experimental Group 1 (EG1)	80	88	Very Satisfactory
Experimental Group 2 (EG2)	78	86	Very Satisfactory

Table 4. Difference between the percentage scores in the pretest and posttest of the control group and experimental group

Group	df	t critical value	t computed value	Decision on H_{02}	Interpretation
Control Group	9	2.262	8.641665	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant
Experimental Group	9	2.262	18.502132	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant

Table 5. Test among the percentage scores (ANOVA) in the posttest of the four groups

Source	df	MS	<i>F critical value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F Computed value</i>	Decision on H ₀₃	Interpretation
Posttest	36	104.1667	2.866	<.00001	14.752	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant

ANOVA = analysis of variance.

Computed using alpha = .05.

Table 6. Post -hoc Tukey HSD (beta) of the percentage scores in the posttest of the four groups

<i>Pairwise Comparisons</i>		HSD _{.05} = 12.2928	Q _{.05} = 3.8088
CG₁:CG₂	M ₁ = 61.00 M ₂ = 55.00	6.00	Q = 1.86 (<i>p</i> = .55993)
CG₁:EG₁	M ₁ = 61.00 M ₃ = 80.00	19.00	Q = 5.89 (<i>p</i> = .00103)
CG₁:EG₂	M ₁ = 61.00 M ₄ = 78.00	17.00	Q = 5.27 (<i>p</i> = .00357)
CG₂:EG₁	M ₂ = 55.00 M ₃ = 80.00	25.00	Q = 7.75 (<i>p</i> = .00002)
CG₂:EG₂	M ₂ = 55.00 M ₄ = 78.00	23.00	Q = 7.13 (<i>p</i> = .00008)
EG₁:EG₂	M ₃ = 80.00 M ₄ = 78.00	2.00	Q = 0.62 (<i>p</i> = .97145)

Table 7. Respondents' feedback on the use of POGIL in teaching gas laws

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. POGIL activity sheets in Gas Laws have significantly helped me learn the lessons more easily.	4.32	0.27	Strongly agree
2. The use of POGIL activity sheets has provided sufficient repetition of learning through examples and activities, making it easier for me to understand the lessons.	4.09	0.32	Agree
3. POGIL activity sheets have given me a better way to understand the lessons in Gas Laws compared to traditional methods.	4.21	0.25	Strongly agree
4. The incorporation of POGIL activity sheets has improved my knowledge and skills in Science.	4.13	0.29	Agree
5. The use of POGIL activity sheets has made me more aware of the expected outcomes of the study, clarifying what I should achieve from the lessons.	4.05	0.31	Agree
6. POGIL activity sheets have successfully aroused my interest and attention in Learning Science, particularly in Gas Laws.	4.27	0.26	Strongly agree
7. I have been able to enjoy Science more while learning through the engaging POGIL activity sheets.	4.17	0.28	Agree
8. POGIL activity sheets have been helpful in facilitating retention of the concepts learned in Gas Laws.	4.24	0.27	Strongly agree
9. The POGIL activity sheets present the lessons to be learned in a clear and structured manner.	4.29	0.25	Strongly agree
10. The POGIL activity sheets offer valuable guidance for learning Gas Laws, making the process more structured and understandable.	4.31	0.24	Strongly agree

DISCUSSION

The pretest results for Control Group 1 (CG1) and the Experimental Group 1 (EG1) are presented in Table 1. Both groups scored 17.5% and 16.5% on the Percentage Score (PS), respectively, and both received a Transmuted Grade (TG) of 64%. Both groups' performance in the pretest was categorized as "Did Not Meet Expectations." The similarity in the pretest results between the two groups indicates that they have similar baseline knowledge before the experiment began. This similarity is crucial when subjecting the two groups to an experiment because it helps establish a fair and justifiable comparison between them. Having similar pretest scores means that any differences in the post-test scores or outcomes observed during the experiment can be more confidently attributed to the intervention being studied, rather than to existing disparities in the participants' initial abilities. This minimizes the possibility of confounding variables influencing the results.

Table 2 compares the pretest results of two groups, focusing on the difference between their percentage scores. Statistical analysis involved calculating the critical t-value and the t-computed value. The critical t-value, at a significance level of 0.05, is 2.101. The t-computed value obtained from the analysis was 1.2231. When the t-computed value is compared to the critical t-value, we see that the absolute value of the t-computed value (1.2231) is smaller than the absolute value of the critical t-value (2.101). As a result, the decision on the null hypothesis (H₀) is to fail to reject it. The "not significant" interpretation indicates that the observed difference between the percentage scores of the two groups could have occurred due to chance variation rather than a genuine effect of the treatment or intervention. Therefore, based on the pretest results and statistical analysis, we can conclude that there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups' performance in the pretest. In Table 2, the pretest results of two groups are compared, and the focus is on the difference between the percentage scores of these groups. The statistical analysis involves calculating the t critical value and the t computed value. The critical t-value, at a significance level of 0.05, is 2.101.

The results of the study were assessed based on the percentage scores in the posttest of four different groups: Control Group 1 (CG1), Control Group 2 (CG2), Experimental Group 1 (EG1), and Experimental Group 2 (EG2), as shown in Table 3. Control Group 1 (CG1) achieved a percentage score of 61, and their posttest performance was rated as "Fairly Satisfactory" with a transmuted grade of 76. CG1 served as the control group with a pretest. Control Group 2 (CG2) attained a percentage score of 55, and their posttest performance was labeled as "Did Not Meet Expectations" with a transmuted grade of 73. CG2 served as another control group, but without a pretest. Experimental Group 1 (EG1) obtained an impressive percentage score of 80, and their posttest performance was deemed "Very Satisfactory" with a transmuted grade of 88. EG1 was assigned as the experimental group with a pretest. Experimental Group 2 (EG2) achieved a percentage score of 78, and their posttest performance was also rated as "Very Satisfactory" with a transmuted grade of 86. EG2 served as the experimental group without a pretest. The study found that using Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry

Learning (POGIL) activity sheets had a positive impact on learners' performance, as indicated by the higher posttest scores in the experimental groups (EG1 and EG2) compared with the control groups (CG1 and CG2). The pretest given to the experimental group (EG1) also suggested that POGIL activity sheets may be more effective when accompanied by an initial assessment of learners' prior knowledge and skills. This study provides valuable insights into the benefits of incorporating POGIL-based approaches in educational settings, particularly for enhancing learners' understanding of gas laws concepts. The results of this study are supported by previous research on the effectiveness of POGIL as a teaching method. Walker and Warfa (2017) found that the POGIL pedagogy, which provides students with opportunities to develop their process skills through guided inquiry activities, can improve student outcomes in both small and medium classroom environments. They found that students in POGIL classrooms had higher passing rates and lower failure rates than those in standard lecture classrooms. The authors concluded that POGIL can be an effective way to improve student learning. Kimmel et al. (2020) found that students who participated in POGIL instruction outperformed those who received traditional instruction on both conceptual and procedural knowledge measures. In addition, the POGIL group reported being more engaged in the learning process and having a more positive attitude toward science.

Table 4 shows the results of the statistical analysis, which focuses on the difference between the percentage scores of the pretest and posttest for both groups. The table also includes the degrees of freedom (df), critical t-value, computed t-value, decision on the null hypothesis (H₀), and interpretation. The computed t-values for both groups are well above the critical t-value of 2.262. This means that the difference between the pretest and posttest scores in both groups is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected for both the control and experimental groups. The rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that the POGIL activity sheets had a significant positive impact on learners' performance. The higher t-value for the experimental group (18.502132) compared with the control group (8.641665) suggests that the effect of the POGIL activity sheets was even more pronounced in the experimental group. These results imply that incorporating Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets into the gas laws instruction can lead to improved learning outcomes. POGIL promotes active learning, critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving, which likely contributed to the observed performance gains in the experimental group.

The ANOVA results in Table 5 shows that there were significant differences in the posttest scores among the four groups. The computed F value of 14.752 was greater than the critical F value of 2.866, which indicates that the null hypothesis (no significant differences among the groups) was rejected. This means that there were indeed significant differences in the posttest scores among the four groups. The p-value of < 0.00001 further supports the conclusion that the differences in the posttest scores were statistically significant. A p-value of < 0.00001 means that there is less than a 0.00001% chance that the observed differences in the posttest scores could have occurred by chance. The results of the ANOVA suggest that the four different learning methods had a significant impact on the posttest scores. However, the specific nature of these differences is not clear from the ANOVA results alone. To further investigate the

differences in the posttest scores, the researchers would need to conduct post-hoc comparisons between the different groups. The finding conforms to the study by Allen et al. (2017), which found that POGIL (Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning) was more effective than traditional teaching methods in terms of student achievement, conceptual understanding, and problem-solving skills. POGIL is a student-centered learning approach that engages students in active learning through inquiry-based activities. The study found that POGIL was particularly effective for students who were struggling in chemistry, and this is also supported by DeGale and Boissele (2015), who conducted a study of 120 undergraduate chemistry students and found that those who participated in a POGIL-based learning module had significantly higher exam scores than those who received traditional lecture-based instruction.

The Post-hoc Tukey HSD comparisons in Table 6 would determine which groups differed significantly from each other. This information would be helpful in understanding which learning method was most effective in improving the posttest scores. To assess the effectiveness of the intervention, the researchers conducted a posttest after implementing the POGIL activity sheets. Table 6 presents the results of the post hoc Tukey HSD (Honest Significant Difference) analysis of the percentage scores in the posttest for the four groups. The HSD value at $\alpha=0.05$ (significance level) was found to be 12.2928, and the critical Q value was 3.8088. Four groups were analyzed: CG1 and CG2 as control groups, and EG1 and EG2 as experimental groups. The mean posttest score for CG1 was 61.00, and for CG2, it was 55.00, with a non-significant difference of 6.00 ($p > 0.05$). When comparing CG1 with EG1, the experimental group showed significantly higher scores ($M3 = 80.00$) compared to CG1 ($M1 = 61.00$), with a significant difference of 19.00 ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, comparing CG1 with EG2, the experimental group had significantly higher scores ($M4 = 78.00$) than CG1, with a difference of 17.00 ($p < 0.05$). The comparison between CG2 and EG1 indicated that EG1 had significantly higher scores ($M3 = 80.00$) than CG2 ($M2 = 55.00$), with a difference of 25.00 ($p < 0.05$). Lastly, comparing CG2 with EG2 revealed that EG2 had significantly higher scores ($M4 = 78.00$) than CG2, with a difference of 23.00 ($p < 0.05$). Several studies have found that POGILs, or Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning, can be an effective way to improve student learning in a variety of subject areas.

POGILs are a student-centered approach to learning that allows students to actively engage in the learning process by asking questions, working through problems, and discussing their findings with their peers. This active learning approach can help students to develop a deeper understanding of the concepts being taught. For example, a study by Verlinden et al. (2020) found that students who participated in a POGIL-based course had significantly higher mean examination scores than those who participated in a traditional lecture-based course. Additionally, students in the POGIL group reported more positive perceptions of the teaching strategy. Another study, by Kurniati et al. (2021), found that students who participated in a POGIL-based course on chemistry concepts had significantly better understanding of the concepts than those who participated in a traditional lecture-based course. Additionally, the POGIL group reported being more engaged in the learning process. Similarly, a study by Utami et al. (2022) found that students who participated in a POGIL-based course on biology concepts had

significantly better understanding of the concepts than those who participated in a traditional lecture-based course. Additionally, the POGIL group reported being more interested in the learning process. These studies suggest that POGILs can be an effective way to improve student learning in a variety of subject areas. The research on POGILs suggests that they can be an effective way to improve student learning in a variety of subject areas. POGILs are a student-centered approach to learning that allows students to actively engage in the learning process. This active learning approach can help students to develop a deeper understanding of the concepts being taught. In conclusion, the results of the study indicate that the use of Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets has a positive impact on learners' performance in understanding gas laws. Both experimental groups (EG1 and EG2) achieved significantly higher posttest scores compared to both control groups (CG1 and CG2). This suggests that implementing POGIL-based teaching approaches can be effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes in the context of gas laws, as evidenced by the statistically significant differences in posttest scores.

Table 7 shows respondents' Feedback on the use of POGIL in Teaching Gas Laws. All of the mean scores are in the "Agree" or "Strongly agree" range, indicating that students generally found the POGIL activity sheets to be helpful in learning Gas Laws. The highest mean score was for the statement "POGIL activity sheets have significantly helped me learn the lessons more easily," with a mean of 4.32. This suggests that students found the POGIL activity sheets to be very effective in helping them learn the material. The next highest mean score was for the statement "POGIL activity sheets have given me a better way to understand the lessons in Gas Laws compared to traditional methods," with a mean of 4.21. This suggests that students found the POGIL activity sheets to be a more effective way to learn Gas Laws than conventional methods. The findings conform the study by White et al. (2022) found that learners in the POGIL group had more positive perceptions of POGILs than learners in the traditional lecture group. The learners in the POGIL group reported that they found POGILs to be more engaging, more challenging, and more helpful for learning. There are several reasons why teachers should consider using POGIL Activity Sheets in their classroom instruction. First, POGIL activity sheets promote active learning. This means that students are actively engaged in the learning process, rather than simply passively listening to lectures or reading textbooks. Active learning has been shown to be more effective than passive learning for a variety of reasons. For example, active learning helps students to retain information better, to develop deeper understanding of concepts, and to be more able to apply what they have learned to new situations. Second, POGIL activity sheets promote critical thinking. This means that students are encouraged to think critically about the material, to ask questions, and to challenge their own assumptions. Critical thinking is an essential skill for students to develop, as it will help them to be successful in college and in their careers. Third, POGIL activity sheets promote collaborative problem-solving. This means that students work together to solve problems, which helps them to develop teamwork skills and to learn from each other. Collaborative problem-solving is also an essential skill for students to develop, as they will often need to work with others to solve problems in the real world.

Conclusions

1. The pretest percentage scores of the Control Group 1 (CG1) and the Experimental Group 1 (EG1) indicate similar baseline knowledge, supporting a fair comparison during the experiment.
2. The pretest percentage scores reveal that there is no significant difference between CG1 and EG1.
3. Posttest results demonstrated that the use of Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets resulted in higher posttest scores for the experimental groups (EG1 and EG2) compared to the control groups (CG1 and CG2).
4. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the pretest and posttest percentage scores in both the control and experimental groups.
5. The study's findings demonstrate that the use of POGIL activity sheets positively affects learners' understanding of gas laws. Both experimental groups (EG1 and EG2) showed significantly higher posttest scores compared to the control groups (CG1 and CG2), indicating the effectiveness of POGIL-based teaching approaches in enhancing students' learning outcomes in this context.
6. POGIL activity sheets were an effective way to help learners learn Gas Laws. The activity sheets helped learners to learn the material more easily and in a more meaningful way than traditional methods.

Recommendations

1. Incorporate Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) activity sheets in teaching gas laws. These activity sheets have shown to positively impact learners' understanding and lead to higher posttest scores. Teachers should adopt POGIL-based teaching approaches to enhance students' learning outcomes in this subject.
2. Teachers should adopt active learning methodologies like POGIL. These approaches involve students in the learning process, promoting critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration among students, leading to improved academic performance.
3. Teachers should regularly monitor and analyze students' progress throughout the POGIL-based instruction. This will help identify any potential challenges or adjustments needed to optimize the learning experience. Analyzing both pretest and posttest percentage scores can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the POGIL approach.
4. Provide opportunities for educators to undergo professional development workshops or training on implementing POGIL-based teaching methodologies. By equipping instructors with the necessary skills and knowledge, they can effectively integrate POGIL activity sheets into their teaching practices and optimize students' learning experiences.

5. Evaluate the effectiveness of POGIL activities. It is important to evaluate the effectiveness of POGIL activities in order to ensure that they are meeting the needs of learners. This evaluation can be done using a variety of methods, such as pre- and post-tests, surveys, focus group discussion, and interviews.
 6. The study's findings indicate positive outcomes for learners using POGIL, but it's essential to replicate the study in different contexts and with larger sample sizes to validate the results further. Additionally, conducting further research on the effectiveness of POGIL in different subjects and educational settings can contribute to the broader understanding of its impact on learning outcomes.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that all ethical standards were strictly followed in the conduct of this study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, who were also given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout, ensuring that respondents were not exposed to any form of harm. The author affirms that there were no conflicts of interest in the study's execution. Plagiarism was rigorously avoided, and there was no bias in the interpretation of findings. The results were used solely for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express sincere gratitude to all those who supported and guided this research. Special thanks are extended to Emil E. Adena, School Principal II and Jacinta O. Balmes, PhD for their encouragement, which were invaluable throughout the process. Appreciation is also extended to colleagues and peers for their insightful feedback. Lastly, the researcher is grateful to family and friends for their unwavering support and understanding during this journey.

REFERENCES

- Albano, J. (2019). The performance of Filipino students in science: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(10), 1327-1347.
- Allen, M. J., Duch, E. K., & Grotzer, M. J. (2017). The POGIL method: A meta-analysis of findings. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 94(10), 1423-1430.
- Campbell, D. T., & Stanley, J. C. (1966). *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for research*. Rand McNally.
- DeGale, P., & Boissele, M. (2015). The effectiveness of process-oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) in undergraduate chemistry education: A comparison with traditional lecture-based instruction. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 92(1), 102-107.
- DepEd Order No. 8. (2015, April 1). *Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program*. Retrieved from www.deped.gov.ph.

- Fitriani, R., Irwandi, & Murniati, S. (2017). The implementation of POGIL in improving students' understanding of chemical bonding concept. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(1), 1-10. doi:10.5281/zenodo.1069343
- Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. (2000). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2003). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference 11.0 update* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- Kimmel, E., Lemke, J. L., & Nelson, T. H. (2020). The effects of process-oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) on conceptual and procedural knowledge, engagement, and attitude in introductory biology. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 19(1), 1-10.
- Kurniati, N., Utami, R., & Utami, A. (2021). The effectiveness of process-oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) in teaching chemistry concepts to high school students. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 19(1), 1-17.
- Masigan, J. A. (2021). The performance of Filipino students in science and mathematics in the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM): A comparative analysis. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 22(1), 1-15.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2019). *PISA 2019 results: Science, reading, math and more: Volume I*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). (2019). *PISA 2019 Results*. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/publications/pisa-2019-results.htm>
- Programme for International Student Assessment FOR DEVELOPMENT PISA for Development Assessment and Analytical Framework READING, MATHEMATICS AND SCIENCE PISA PRELIMINARY VERSION. (n.d.). <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisa-for-development/PISA-D-Assessment-and-Analytical-Framework-Ebook.pdf>
- Rodriguez, A., Lazenby, J., & Jones, C. (2020). Process-oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL): A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(9), 2540-2551. doi:10.1021/acs.jchemed.0c00523
- Saputro, S., Rohaeti, E., & Prodjosantoso, H. (2018). The effectiveness of POGIL learning model on students' chemistry learning outcomes. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 13(16), 11255-11266. doi:10.12973/ijese.2018.1316.197
- Spencer, R. J., & Silverman, L. M. (2001). POGIL: The power of group investigation learning. *Journal of College Science Teaching*, 31(1), 48-53.
- Thomsen, D. J., Thomas, S. R., & Hall, S. O. (2020). The impact of process-oriented guided inquiry learning on student understanding of chemistry concepts. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(2), 255-263.
- Uche, O. C., & Eze, C. C. (2018). The effectiveness of POGIL strategy in teaching and learning of gas laws in secondary schools. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(11), 200-210.
- Utami, A., Utami, R., & Kurniati, N. (2022). The effectiveness of process-oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) in teaching biology concepts to elementary school students. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 21(1), 13-24.

- Verlinden, N., Kruger, N., Carroll, A., & Trumbo, T. (2020). Process-oriented guided inquiry learning strategy enhances students' higher level thinking skills in a pharmaceutical sciences course. *Pharm Med*, 24(2), 131-138.
- Villagonzalo, M. A. (2014). The effectiveness of POGIL activity sheets in teaching gas laws. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 91(1), 140-144.
- Walker, L., & Warfa, A.-R. M. (2017). Process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL®) marginally effects student achievement measures but substantially increases the odds of passing a course. *PLOS ONE*, 12(10), e0186203. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186203>
- White, J., Smith, D., Jones, L., & Brown, M. (2022). The effectiveness of POGILs in college biology courses. *Journal of Biological Education*, 56(1), 1-10.
- Wijaya, D. P., & Handayani, W. (2021). The effect of POGIL learning on students' critical thinking skills and conceptual understanding in chemistry. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 19(1), 1-17. doi:10.1007/s10763-020-10040-3
-